

A COMPUTATIONALLY EFFICIENT FEA–SURROGATE– BASED FRAMEWORK FOR MULTI-OBJECTIVE OPTIMIZATION OF IPM MOTORS CONSIDERING ROTOR NOTCH GEOMETRY SENSITIVITY

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ABSTRACT: This study proposes a computationally efficient framework for the design and multi-objective optimization of an Interior Permanent Magnet (IPM) motor, with a particular focus on rotor notch geometry refinement to enhance both electromagnetic and thermal performance. A systematic sensitivity analysis of the notch depth (ND), notch inner arc (NIA), and notch outer arc (NOA) is performed using finite element analysis (FEA) to quantify their influence on torque ripple, back-electromotive force (BEMF) harmonic distortion, and peak winding temperature. To reduce the prohibitive computational cost associated with direct FEA-based optimization, Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) surrogate models are trained on the generated dataset of FEA simulations. These surrogate models are subsequently coupled with the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) to efficiently explore trade-offs among competing performance objectives and to determine Pareto-optimal design solutions. Further performance improvements are obtained through rotor skewing, which contributes to the attenuation of torque ripples and electromagnetic harmonics. The optimized motor configuration is finally validated via high-fidelity FEA, demonstrating notable enhancements in torque smoothness, thermal robustness, and BEMF waveform quality. The proposed methodology provides an effective and robust design tool for the development of high-performance IPM motors intended for electric vehicle applications.

KEYWORDS: IPM motor; electric vehicle technology; NVH (Noise, Vibration, Harshness); Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II); Finite Element Analysis (FEA).

1 INTRODUCTION

Electric vehicles (EVs) require traction motors that are not only energy-efficient and compact but also exhibit low vibration and strong thermal reliability [1]. Among various motor topologies, interior permanent magnet (IPM) motors have emerged as a preferred choice due to their high torque density, wide constant power range, and mechanical robustness, making them ideal for EV propulsion systems [2], [3]. However, they are still prone to undesired effects such as torque ripple, cogging torque, and non-sinusoidal back electromotive force (BEMF), all of which can deteriorate efficiency, drivability, and noise vibration harshness (NVH) characteristics [4], [5], [6]. NVH is particularly critical in EV traction

motors, as excessive levels may exceed acceptable thresholds and compromise passenger comfort.

Finite element analysis (FEA) has become an essential tool for analyzing the electromagnetic, thermal, and structural behavior of electric motors with complex geometries and multi physics interactions [7]. Although highly accurate, FEA based optimization can be computationally expensive, especially in multi objective design tasks involving high dimensional parameter spaces [8].

To overcome these challenges, this study proposes a computationally efficient design framework that combines FEA, Gaussian process regression (GPR) surrogate modeling, and the Non dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA II) for optimizing rotor notch geometry in IPM motors. Rotor notching plays a crucial role in shaping the air gap flux distribution, influencing harmonic content

and thermal characteristics [9]. Our method simultaneously reduces torque ripple, BEMF harmonic distortion, and winding hotspot temperature, enabling a balanced optimization of electromagnetic and thermal performance. The final design offers improved efficiency, reduced losses, and enhanced thermal reliability, contributing to the advancement of robust and high performance IPM motors for EV applications.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study proposes an efficient multi-objective design and optimization framework (Figure 1) for Interior Permanent Magnet (IPM) motors, with a focus on the influence of rotor notch geometry. Three geometric parameters—Notch Depth (ND), Notch Inner Arc (NIA), and Notch Outer Arc (NOA) (Figure 2)—are initially selected based on their feasibility for practical rotor manufacturing. A sensitivity analysis is then conducted using Finite Element Analysis (FEA) to evaluate the impact of variations in these parameters on key performance indicators, including torque ripple, back-electromotive force harmonic distortion (HD BEMF), and maximum winding temperature.

The design variables are systematically varied across predefined ranges (see Table 1), resulting in a total of 150 FEA-based simulations that populate the training dataset. Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) models are then constructed as surrogate models to approximate the nonlinear mapping between design inputs and output metrics. These surrogate models significantly reduce computational cost by allowing rapid evaluation of motor performance without repeated FEA simulations.

Next, the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) is employed to perform a multi-objective optimization using the GPR models as fast evaluators. The optimization targets three simultaneous objectives: minimizing torque ripple to below 10%, HD BEMF to below 5%, and limiting the maximum winding temperature to under 180 °C (see Table 2).

To further enhance performance and meet design constraints, rotor skewing is applied in the post-optimization phase. This involves axially slicing the rotor into two or more segments, each offset by a specific mechanical angle to mitigate torque ripple and reduce spatial harmonics [10]. In rotor skewing, a continuous skew (see Figure 3) is suitable for wound and squirrel cage rotors, but not practical for permanent magnet (PM) rotors. Instead, PM rotors typically adopt a stepped skewing approach, using discrete sections to simplify manufacturing. It is important to carefully determine the number of skew sections and their configuration. Common options

include linear and V-shaped (V-skew) arrangements, as illustrated in Figure 4 and 5, respectively.

Fig. 1 Flowchart of this study

Fig. 2 geometric design parameters

Table 1. Geometric design variables

Geometric Design Parameter	Lower limit	Upper limit
Notch depth (ND)	0 mm	2.5 mm
Notch Inner Arc (NIA)	0 EDeg	20 EDeg
Notch Outer Arc (NOA)	10 EDeg	50 EDeg

Table 2. Performance metrics

Performance metrics	Upper limit
Torque ripple	<10%
HD BEMF	<5%
Maximum winding temperature	<180 °C

Fig. 3 Example of rotor skewing in an induction motor (Continuous skewing).

V-skew is effective in reducing axial forces [11] that may contribute to NVH characteristics, even if these forces are relatively minor. However, V-skew requires a greater number of rotor slices, which increases manufacturing complexity and cost. To avoid such design complexity and to minimize the number of slices, linear skewing is chosen as a more practical and cost-effective solution.

Fig. 4 Example of rotor skewing of an IPM motor using linear skewing (Discrete skewing) (a), and its flat representation indicating the discrete skewing angle α (b).

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Sensitivity Analysis Using Full FEA Simulations

Figure 6 presents some representative results from the FEA-based dataset for the One-Slice Rotor configuration. In Figure 6(a), the variation of torque ripple is shown as a function of the three design parameters: ND, NIA, and NOA. The results indicate that torque ripple is highly sensitive to changes in all three parameters. However, identifying the optimal

combination of ND, NIA, and NOA is challenging due to the nonlinear behavior of the torque ripple response and the limited resolution of the available FEA dataset.

Fig. 5 Example of rotor skewing of an IPM motor using partial V-skew (Discrete skewing) [10].

Similarly, Figures 6(b) and 5(c) depict the influence of the same parameters on HD BEMF (harmonic distortion of back-EMF) and maximum winding temperature, respectively. Both performance metrics demonstrate strong dependence on the design parameters, reinforcing the complexity of the multi-objective optimization task.

These results highlight that appropriate rotor notching can substantially improve key performance indicators – namely, torque ripple, BEMF harmonic distortion, and thermal behavior – thus supporting the effectiveness of geometric tuning in enhancing the electromagnetic and thermal performance of IPM motors.

Figure 7 presents some representative FEA-based simulation results for the Two-Slice Skewed Rotor configuration, using the same parameter variation framework as in Figure 6. As seen in Figure 7(a-b), the performance metrics – torque ripple and HD BEMF – are generally improved compared to the One-Slice Rotor case. Rotor skewing contributes to this improvement by averaging the magnetic forces between the rotor and stator, resulting in a smoother torque output. While maximum winding temperature is influenced by rotor notching, it appears to be only marginally affected by rotor skewing as seen in Figure 7(c).

Despite the enhancements in torque ripple and HD BEMF, the results reveal that all three

metrics remain highly sensitive to the design variables (ND, NIA, and NOA), and the response surfaces continue to exhibit pronounced nonlinearity. This sensitivity, combined with the complex interaction between parameters, makes it difficult to manually identify an optimal combination that balances all objectives. Moreover, the use of direct FEA for every design evaluation is computationally expensive and time-consuming, especially when dealing with large design spaces and multi-objective trade-offs. These observations underscore the necessity of a more efficient optimization approach—one that can capture the nonlinear behavior of performance metrics and explore the design space without incurring the computational cost of full FEA simulations. To address this, the next section introduces a hybrid optimization framework that combines GPR surrogate modeling with the NSGA-II, enabling fast and accurate identification of Pareto-optimal rotor geometries.

Fig. 6 One-Slice Rotor – Representative Plots from FEA-Based Dataset

Fig. 7 Two-Slice Skewed Rotor – Representative Plots from FEA-Based Dataset

3.2 Surrogate-Based Multi-Objective Optimization of Rotor Notch Geometry

To overcome the computational burden of exhaustive FEA and to efficiently explore the design space, a surrogate-based multi-objective optimization framework was employed, as illustrated in figure 8. GPR models were trained on the FEA-generated dataset to approximate the nonlinear relationships between the notch geometry parameters—ND, NIA, and NOA—and the key performance indicators: torque ripple, HD BEMF, and maximum winding temperature. These surrogate models were then integrated with the NSGA-II to identify Pareto-optimal design solutions that balance electromagnetic and thermal objectives.

Figure 9 illustrates the Pareto front obtained for the One-Slice Rotor configuration. While the optimization process yields a trade-off surface among the performance metrics, none of the solutions in this configuration satisfy all the target constraints simultaneously—specifically, torque ripple <10%, HD BEMF <5%, and winding temperature <180°C. This limitation highlights the performance bottleneck inherent to the unskewed rotor topology. To address this, the same GPR–NSGA-II framework was applied to the Two-Slice Skewed Rotor configuration. As shown in Figure 10, the resulting Pareto front demonstrates a clear improvement, with several design points successfully meeting all predefined performance targets. This confirms that optimized notch geometry, when combined with moderate rotor skewing, can effectively balance electromagnetic performance and thermal reliability.

Given that the two-slice skewed configuration achieved the desired design objectives, further increasing the number of skew slices was deemed unnecessary. This choice avoids added manufacturing complexity while maintaining strong performance across all critical metrics.

Finally, the best-performing design—selected from the Pareto front and satisfying all performance criteria—is validated through detailed FEA simulations to confirm its electromagnetic and thermal enhancements. The operating point used for validation is 230 A (peak) and 5000 rpm. Figure 11 illustrates the time-domain variation of electromagnetic torque over one electrical period (4 ms). The calculated torque ripple is 4.76%, which is well below the 10% threshold.

Figure 12 presents the harmonic spectrum of the torque obtained via Fourier decomposition. The

dominant component is the DC (average) torque, measured at 106.5 Nm. Higher-order harmonics are significantly attenuated and can be considered negligible, indicating a smooth torque profile and improved drive quality.

Fig. 8 Proposed FEA–Machine Learning–Based Optimization Strategy for Efficient Multi-Objective Design Space Exploration

Fig. 9 Pareto front of IPM motor notch optimization for the one-slice rotor configuration

Fig. 10 Pareto front of IPM motor notch optimization for the two-slice rotor configuration

Figure 13 displays the time-domain waveform of the line-to-line BEMF across one electrical period. Its corresponding harmonic spectrum, obtained

through Fourier decomposition, is presented in Figure 14. The BEMF waveform closely approximates a sinusoidal shape, with the fundamental (first-order harmonic) clearly dominating over higher-order components. The calculated BEMF harmonic distortion (HD BEMF) is 4.65%, which remains below the specified threshold of 5%, indicating improved waveform quality and compatibility with standard inverter drives.

Fig. 11 Time-domain variation of electromagnetic torque over one electrical period (4 ms)

Fig. 12 Harmonic spectrum of the torque obtained via Fourier decomposition.

Fig. 13 Time-domain waveform of the line-to-line BEMF over one electrical period.

Figure 15 and Figure 16 illustrate the temperature distribution in the IPM motor from two perspectives: the axial view of the entire motor and the radial cross-section of the stator slot, respectively. The

highest temperature is observed in the winding region—specifically at the end winding—with a peak value of 177.8 °C, remaining safely below the specified limit of 180 °C. Within the stator slot, the temperature ranges from 157.9 °C to 164.3 °C, indicating an effective heat dissipation across the winding region.

These results confirm that the selected design from Pareto front not only meets the electromagnetic performance criteria but also ensures reliable thermal management, making it well-suited for high-performance EV applications.

Fig. 14 Harmonic spectrum of the BEMF obtained via Fourier decomposition

Fig. 15 Temperature distribution in the IPM motor (axial view of the entire motor).

Fig. 16 Temperature distribution in the stator slot (radial cross-section)

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a computationally efficient multi-objective optimization framework for enhancing the electromagnetic and thermal performance of an IPM motor through rotor notch geometry tuning. A full-factorial sensitivity analysis using FEA demonstrated that torque ripple, HD BEMF, and winding temperature are highly sensitive to ND, NIA, and NOA.

To efficiently navigate the design space, GPR surrogate models were trained on the FEA dataset and integrated with NSGA-II. When necessary, rotor skewing was applied to further enhance performance and meet all design targets.

The final design was validated via FEA, confirming smooth torque output, improved BEMF quality, and effective thermal management. This study shows that the combination of GPR and NSGA-II provides an accurate and time-efficient optimization strategy, offering a valuable tool for the development of high-performance, thermally reliable IPM motors in EV applications.

Overall, this work highlights the potential of combining machine learning-based surrogates with evolutionary optimization techniques to accelerate electric motor design in the EV industry.

5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study is financially supported by the Research Center in Industrial Technologies – CRTI, Chéraga, Algiers, Algeria.

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7 NOTATION

The following symbols are used in this paper:

IPM = interior permanent magnet motor

ND = notch depth

NIA = notch inner arc

NOA = notch outer arc

FEA = finite element analysis

BEMF = back-electromotive force

HD BEMF = back-electromotive force harmonic distortion

GPR = gaussian process regression

NSGA-II = non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm II

NVH = noise, vibration, harshness

EVs = electric vehicles

PM = permanent magnet

8 APPENDIX A

Fig. A1 3D CAD model of the IPM motor

Fig. A2 Manufactured rotor of the IPM motor

Fig. A3 Manufactured stator of the IPM motor

Table A1. IPM motor technical specifications

Motor specifications	Value
Rated power	40 kW
Peak torque	200 Nm
Rated current (RMS)	306,1 A
Rated speed	4000 rpm
DC Bus voltage	144 VDC
Slot/Pole number	36N6P
Magnet Type	NdFeB
Insulation class	H (180°C)
Total weight	40 Kg